

Exploring Sustainable Approaches to Coloration: A Review

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Abstract:

For centuries, humans have relied on a variety of nature's palette in their search for color. It wasn't until the middle of the 18th century that synthetic dyes were commercially used which transformed the world of coloration. The commercial utilization of synthetic dyes is steadily increasing across various sectors, including textiles, leather, paper, printing ink, food, medical and health care, plastic, rubber, cosmetics, paint and coatings, and many others. The annual global production of synthetic dyes exceeds 1,000,000 tons, with the textile sector alone consuming 80% of this quantity. Toxicity, non-biodegradability, persistence, and bioaccumulation are the factors that make synthetic dyes a major concern. Synthetic dyes can significantly affect the environment and human health at different stages of their life cycle, including during manufacturing, during application, during usage, and during disposal. Due to the extensive effects of synthetic dyes, there is a pressing need for safer practices. To achieve sustainable coloration, there are various pathways, including dye effluent treatment, regulatory oversight on synthetic dyes, adopting eco-friendly dyes, low-emission dyeing technologies, awareness and education, and collaborative approaches. These strategies can together contribute in reducing the overall ecological footprint of textile industry.

Keywords: Environmental Impacts, Human Health, Natural dyes, Sustainable Approaches, Synthetic Dyes

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1. Introduction

Colors have played a major role in expressing culture, identity, and creativity throughout history. Color elevates the world in infinite ways and there lies the use of dyes. Dyes are complex organic compounds which impart color to materials, making them visually appealing. For centuries, humans have relied on a variety of nature's palette in their search for coloration. It wasn't until the middle of the 18th century that synthetic dyes were commercially used which transformed the world of color. Accordingly dyes are divided into two categories: natural and synthetic, which are further categorized based on various criteria as illustrated in figure 1 [1-7].

The commercial utilization of synthetic dyes is steadily increasing across various sectors, including textiles, leather, paper, printing ink, food, medical and health care, plastic, rubber, cosmetics, paint and coatings, and many others. The annual global production of synthetic dyes exceeds 1,000,000 tons, with the textile sector alone consuming 80% of this quantity [8, 9]. The textile dye market comprises of three main subsectors: clothing, home textile, and industrial textile.

Clothing and apparel form the dominant sector within the textile industry with 59.4% of market share [10, 11]. The global market for textile dyes exhibits a varied distribution across different regions worldwide, including North America, Europe, Asia-Pacific, Latin America, and the Middle East and Africa [12]. More than 35% of the global textile dye market was held by the Asia-Pacific region in 2023, with more than 60% of global production from China, and about 15% of the total global output from India [11, 13].

Figure 1: Classification of dyes [1-7]

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2. Impacts of synthetic dyes

The factors that make synthetic dyes a significant concern are toxicity, non-biodegradability, persistence, and bioaccumulation

- **Toxicity:** Synthetic dyes present a range of environmental and health hazards due to their chemical composition and the by-products they release during production, usage, and disposal processes. The production and utilization of certain dyes releases heavy metals into the environment, which is highly toxic [14-16]. Azo dyes break down into carcinogenic aromatic amines in the environment or inside the human body when absorbed through the skin, ingested, and inhaled posing a risk to ecosystem and human health. Certain dye, such reactive, vat, and disperse dyes contain halogen atoms such as chlorine, bromine, and iodine within their molecular structure, having potential to cause genetic mutations, cancer, and reproductive and developmental abnormalities [15, 17]. Dyes can even react with their intermediate compound, leading to the creation of further toxic substances with mutagenic and carcinogenic properties [18, 19].
- **Non-biodegradability:** Another major concern with synthetic dyes is their non-biodegradability, making them resistant to degradation due to their complex chemical structures. As a result, synthetic dyes are highly resistant to breaking down in natural environments [20, 21].
- **Persistence:** Due to their non-biodegradability, synthetic dyes once enter the environment, persist for extended periods [21]. Persisted dyes can be transported from their point of discharge, spreading toxicity far and wide. This prolonged presence of dyes in the environment increases the likelihood of exposure for various organisms, continuously harming ecosystems, and posing long-term risks to human health [22].
- **Bioaccumulation:** Due to their persistent nature, these dye toxicants accumulate in sediments, soil, and water bodies. They can enter organisms directly from their surroundings or through the food chain, building up in the tissues of these organisms [23]. Small organisms like aquatic plants and terrestrial plants absorb these toxicants, which then get concentrated within the food chain. This leads to a greater buildup in higher trophic levels among predators, including fish, birds, and animals, and eventually humans, who are exposed to the highest levels of contaminants [24]. Whether the human exposure to dyes is through the food chain or through direct contact with the human body, toxic effects can be short-term and long-term. The short-term effects include skin irritation and dermatitis, respiratory issues, gastrointestinal distress, eye irritation, muscle and joint pain. On the other hand, long-term effects on the humans are carcinogenic, mutagenic, hematological, cellular, neurological damage, kidney and liver damage, endocrine disruption, chronic respiratory conditions,

immune system suppression, and skin sensitization [16, 24].

Synthetic dyes can significantly affect the environment and human health at different stages of their life cycle, including during manufacturing, application, consumer usage, and disposal.

2.1 During manufacturing

The synthetic dye manufacturing process generates various hazardous chemicals, dye residues, and by-products which ultimately get disposed of in the environment, thus affecting the ecosystem. The manufacturing process also poses risk to the workers in the plant. Inhalation of dust, fine particles and generated fumes can give rise to respiratory issues, affect a person's immune system, leading to a severe reaction upon subsequent exposure to the dye through inhalation, called respiratory sensitization that can cause itching, watery eyes, sneezing, running nose, blocked airways, and asthma symptoms like coughing and wheezing [25, 26]. Workers also come in contact with raw materials and dyes through their skin, which can cause skin allergic issues, like irritation, rashes, and dermatitis. These dye chemicals can also enter the body through the skin where they can transform into more harmful compounds that can cause genetic mutations and cellular disruptions by interacting with DNA, causing uncontrolled cell growth, leading to cancer and tumor formation [15, 24].

2.2 During application

The azo, anthraquinone, and phthalocyanine type dyes are the most significant ones in the textile industry [27]. The stage at which dyes are used in the textile industry is illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2: Stages of dye application in the textile industry (Author's own)

Workers are also exposed to synthetic dyes during their application (dyeing and printing), causing similar health issues as discussed in section 2.1. Along with dyes other chemicals are also used during dyeing and printing such as dispersants, salts, powder binding agents, anti-foaming agents, anti-freezing agents, thickeners, buffer systems etc. These chemicals further pose their own toxic effects on the workers and the environment [15].

During the dyeing process, not all colors applied to fabrics adhere permanently, instead, percentage of these colors are often left unfixed and subsequently rinsed out [18, 25]. The extent of dye loss varies by dye class, with 2% for basic dyes to up to 50% for reactive dyes [15, 28]. Additionally, insufficient dyeing processes and incomplete dye exhaustion contribute to the release of dyes into wastewater [25, 29]. The discharge of this untreated or inadequately treated dye effluent in water body or onto land, poses significant environmental challenges [18, 22]. Here are the impacts of synthetic dye effluent discharge in the environment:

2.1.1 Impact on aquatic environment

- **Reduced freshwater availability:** One of the most significant impacts of dyeing processes is water pollution [30]. Synthetic dyes, when introduced into water bodies, compromise both surface and groundwater quality. This contamination renders water unfit for consumption and reduces freshwater availability, thereby exacerbating water scarcity and posing significant risks to human health and ecosystem functioning.
- **Physiochemical alterations:** Synthetic dyes in effluents can significantly alter the color of the receiving water body even at small concentrations, indicating water pollution [20, 29] and may also produce foul smell due to organic compounds undergoing various biochemical reactions within the water [24]. By introducing this organic load into the aquatic environment, synthetic dyes also increase levels of biochemical oxygen demand (BOD) and chemical oxygen demand (COD) [14, 19 & 21]. Synthetic dyes can influence water pH, causing fluctuations that can result in either acidic or alkaline conditions, depending on the specific chemical composition of the dye [24, 28].
- **Effect on aquatic plants:** Synthetic dyes in effluents often contain a huge number of suspended dye particles, which form a layer on the surface of the receiving water body, obstructing the penetration of sunlight to the depth of aquatic environments [15, 30 & 31]. Consequently, the amount of light reaching submerged aquatic plants is diminished, compromising their photosynthetic activity. This disruption in photosynthesis impairs plant's ability to produce energy resulting in reduced growth rate or even death. This reduces oxygen production, which is ultimately harmful to aquatic organisms, altering the entire aquatic ecology [14, 18 & 32]. Having dyes in aquatic ecosystems also has a substantial impact on growth, pigment content, mineral and nutrient levels,

protein synthesis, and metabolic processes of aquatic plants [21, 30].

- **Response from aquatic animals:** Due to their close touch with the aquatic ecosystem through their gills, aquatic vertebrates are highly susceptible to the impacts of aquatic pollutants [30]. The presence of suspended synthetic dye particles in the water can block the flow of water through the gills of these organisms, hindering gas exchange and potentially leading to reduced growth rates or even death. Research has uncovered various consequences for aquatic animals, including behavioral and physiological stress, histopathological changes, liver issues, enzymatic activity disturbance, hematological abnormalities, decreased larvae survival, decreased feeding rates, and loss of protein, carbohydrate, and lipid content in tissues [24].

2.2.2 Impact on terrestrial environment

Synthetic dyes also impact land-based environments, primarily stemming from soil contamination. Dyes can infiltrate the soil via direct effluent discharge, irrigation with untreated wastewater, and seepage from contaminated water bodies. The adverse effects on terrestrial ecosystems are as follows:

- **Soil degradation:** Dye waste can lead to deteriorated soil quality, health and productivity by altering its structure, chemistry, and fertility. When dye-containing effluent infiltrates soil, it accumulates and obstructs soil pores, leading to soil compaction. This compaction limits root permeability, hindering plant growth and nutrient uptake, ultimately compromising health and productivity of vegetation [18, 25 & 26].
- **Impact on soil microbial communities:** Soil microorganisms are crucial in maintaining soil health and fertility by decomposing organic matter, cycling nutrients, and suppressing plant pathogens. Synthetic dyes can harm these microorganisms, upsetting soil functions essential for ecosystem health [24, 25].
- **Impact on plant life:** The contamination of soil by synthetic dye pollutants can significantly alter plant communities of contaminated area. These plants are constrained by oxidative stress, which reduces protein content, photosynthesis rates, and the ability to absorb CO₂ [18]. The presence of synthetic dye pollutants diminishes chlorophyll content in the plant, impairs root growth thus disrupting the ability of root system to take up water and nutrients, and inhibits seed germination [24].
- **Groundwater contamination:** The synthetic dye effluent, when released onto land, leads to the accumulation of dyes in sediments [19]. Over time, this accumulation can result in the leaching of toxic pollutants into underground aquifers, thereby contaminating groundwater sources which further transported to public water supply systems [18].

2.3 During consumer usage

The prolonged contact with synthetic dyed clothing, allows sensitive and toxic dye chemicals to be absorbed by skin epithelial tissues, especially when the body is warm and pores are open due to perspiration. The absorbed dye contents can disrupt the skin's metabolism and potentially trigger allergic reactions, including skin rashes, headaches, trouble concentrating, nausea, diarrhea, fatigue, muscle and joint pain, dizziness, difficulty breathing, an irregular heartbeat, and seizures [15, 30]. Apart from these allergic reactions, dye chemicals absorbed also cause various long-term health effects.

2.4 During disposal

After their end of life, textiles often end up in landfills, which can lead to soil contamination with dye chemicals, heavy metals, and other toxic substances found in synthetic dye. This is because synthetic dyes do not degrade under natural conditions, instead accumulate in landfills and leach into the soil, eventually entering the environment. This contamination in the soil adversely affects various components of the ecosystem as discussed in section 2.2.2. Thus synthetic dyes continue to exhibit harmful effects on the environment even long after the disposal of synthetic-dyed textiles.

3 Pathways to sustainable coloration

3.1 Dye-effluent treatment

To protect the ecosystem from dye effluent, it is essential to treat these effluents which can be achieved through physical, chemical or biological methods or combinations of them. Physical and chemical effluent treatment methods are widely used in treating dye-containing wastewater but have several disadvantages, including high investment, operational and maintenance costs, high electricity consumption, and generation of large amounts of sludge and undesirable and harmful by-products. Biological methods, on the other hand, are more promising due to cost-effectiveness, easy application, energy-saving, less sludge, and fewer chemicals needed. However, they are less effective in the short term and require long period of time to yield results [1, 24]. Several studies indicated that no current treatment method can completely remove the color and toxic elements from the dye-containing wastewater. Therefore, immediate attention is required to develop more efficient approaches that are applicable at large scale with economic feasibility.

3.2 Regulatory oversight on synthetic dyes

To oversee the safety, use, and production of synthetic dyes and the discharge of dye-containing effluents, various regulatory bodies have been established, aiming to reduce hazardous chemicals and improve worker safety. Some of the major regulatory bodies ensuring environmental and human safety include Central Pollution Control Board (CPCB), Ministry of Ecology and Environment (MEE), Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), Occupational

Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), European Chemicals Agency (ECHA), and others. There are also several standards and certifications prevalent worldwide regarding dyes, including Bluesign, Global Organic Textile Standard (GOTS), Cradle to Cradle (C2C), OEKO-TEX® ECO PASSPORT, and Zero Discharge of Hazardous Chemicals (ZDHC) to ensure that the dye is free from hazardous chemicals, and have lower environmental impact. Regulatory efforts have discontinued the manufacturing and use of certain hazardous dyestuff and related chemicals, still the gaps in the industry persist. Despite the prohibition of dyes having potential of forming carcinogenic amines, many of them are still on the market [19, 24]. Also, the standards and regulation regarding removal of dyes from effluent are getting more stringent [28] still there are evidences reported of severe dye pollution in water bodies. Recently, blue water was found flowing through taps in Southeast Delhi due to the denim textile mill in the nearby village illegally dumping untreated toxic effluent into the local water bodies [33].

3.3 Adopting eco-friendly dyes

3.3.1 Revival of natural dyes

By returning to natural dyes, we can tap into one of the best options for sustainable coloration. The leading dye manufacturing companies have started introducing new product lines of plant-based natural dyes, like Archroma, DyStar, Huntsman, Tinctoria di Quaregna, Sodhani Biotech, AMA Herbal. Many clothing brands worldwide have switched to natural dyes, in pursuit to achieve sustainable goal. The big companies, such as Levi's, Converse, Mango, H&M, Pangaia, Ralph Lauren, G-Star Raw, Organic Basics, and others are progressively including natural dyes in their ranges. Homegrown clothing brands are also embracing sustainability by turning to natural dyes, including Valani (United States), Sustain by Kat (United States), Ziran (United States), Aranya Naturals (India), 11.11 / Eleven Eleven (India), Upasana (India), Shibui (India), Modern Shibori (United States), Akané Studio (India), Rosemarie Textiles (United States), Rifò (Italy), Story Mfg. (United Kingdom) and so on.

Additionally, various designers around the world are contributing to the goal of sustainable coloration by introducing their collections dyed with natural and eco-friendly dyes. Some of these designers are, Eileen Fisher (United States), Rahul Mishra (India), Rajesh Pratap Singh (India), Naushad Ali (India), Stella McCartney (United Kingdom), Aboubakar Fofana (France), Harris Tweed (Scotland), Aurelie Fontan (United Kingdom) and many others.

Although the adoption of natural dyes is on the rise but its current application is still minimal relative to the vast use of synthetic dyes in the industry. In the textile dye market, synthetic dyes dominate with 91.4% share, far outperforming natural dyes [11]. This is due to the challenges in using natural dye, including their high cost, limited color

palettes, and other difficulties with scaling up their production. However, lots of researches are underway to enhance the extraction and optimization of natural dyes from various sources, ensuring they meet commercial standards for colorfastness and consistency.

3.2.2 Formulating low-impact dyes

- Low-dusting dyes: Dye powder can release fine particles when handled, mixed or applied, lead to skin contact and inhalation of this dye dust, introducing skin sensitization and respiratory issues. Low-dusting dyes such as granular, dust-suppressed or liquid form reduces the workplace health risks associated with dye dust exposure [16].
- The carcinogenicity of dyes that produce carcinogenic metabolites can be mitigated by using non-carcinogenic analogues of the amines and by ensuring that their metabolites are water soluble [16].
- In an effort to reduce the environmental impact, many dye manufacturing companies have developed engineered low-impact dyes. Archroma introduced DIRESUL® EVOLUTION BLACK LIQ, an eco-advanced sulfur black dyestuff that has overall impact reduction to 57% compared to the synthesis of standard sulfur black dyestuff in all 3 endpoints: resources, human health, and ecosystems [34]. Another launch by Achroma, Nylosan® Navy S-3R and Black S-3N are two new metal-free and halogen-free acid dyes, especially to dye polyamide and blends. These dyes enhance resource efficiency, reducing water usage, and CO₂ emissions during dying process [35]. Huntsman Textile Effects introduced AVITERA® Black SE reactive dye reduces water and energy consumption by up to 50% in the processing. Furthermore, the excellent washing-off performance of this dye shortens processing time and increases productivity [36].

3.2.3 Biotechnological advancements of dyes

Biotechnology allows dye production by genetically modifying microorganisms such as bacteria, algae, fungi, and yeast with color-producing genes, which are then grown in a controlled environment and fermented to produce the desired color. Colorifix (United Kingdom) is the first company that used genetically modified microbes to produce and fix dyes onto textiles [37]. It claims that microbial dyeing reduces chemical and water consumption by 80% and 77% respectively and cuts carbon dioxide emission by 31%, thus minimizing environmental burden of dyeing [38]. Similarly, Living Ink Company (United States) has transformed algae biomass into black dye, ALGAE BLACK™ [39]. An Indian company, KBCols, have also produced dyes by using microbes that are suitable for various industrial applications including textiles [40].

Microbial dyes offer several advantages over conventional synthetic dyes, including biodegradability, less use of

chemicals and water, and producing no toxic waste, eliminating the generation of harmful effluent and its treatment. Also, microbial dyes are safe for the workers as they are non-allergic and non-carcinogenic [39, 41]. Despite these benefits, the use of these dyes in dyeing fabrics in industry is currently very limited in practice due to high cost [42].

3.4 Emerging low-emission dyeing technologies

- Plasma treatment: This technology modifies the surface characteristics of polymeric and textile substrates, enhancing the hydrophilic properties of fibers and textiles. This improves their dye ability and making the process effluent-free and thus eco-friendly. It also reduces water and chemical usage, energy consumption, and eliminates drying processes [1, 43].
- Supercritical Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) dyeing: This process utilizes supercritical CO₂ (a state where CO₂ behaves as both a liquid and a gas) as a solvent for dyes. The CO₂ thus permeates and swells the textile fibers, allowing for waterless dyeing with high dye diffusion and reduced energy consumption, thereby optimizing the dyeing process [1, 43]. Major brands such as IKEA, Adidas, and Nike have adopted this technology [44].
- AirDye® technology: This technology utilizes sublimation process to transfer inks to fabrics using transfer paper combined with heat and pressure, eliminating the need for water and chemicals. The paper used in the process can be recycled and also allows dyes to revert to their original state for reuse, thus reducing emissions by 84% and producing no harmful byproducts [1].
- Ultrasonic dyeing: This technology involves the introduction of ultrasonic waves into the dye bath in order to enhance the dye dispersion, degassing, and diffusion within fibers [1, 43]. Levis brand have used this technology in its Wellthread® collection of 2015 [45].
- Microwave technology: This technology uses microwave energy to heat the dye bath which enhances the diffusion of dye molecules within polymers. This process yields high exhaustion rates, promotes extensive dye diffusion, and ensures superior color fastness properties [1].
- Nano-Dye™ technology: This process represents a continuous dyeing system where reactive dye molecules are maintained in individual nano states to integrate into cellulose. This method eliminates the need for salt, reduced water and energy usage by up to 75%, and achieving up to 97% dye exhaustion [1].
- Electrochemical reduction dyeing: This technology involves the reduction of dyes by using electrochemical reaction, making them suitable for application to fabrics. This process basically involves the addition of electron to

a dye molecule, thus reducing its oxidation state which is facilitated by applying an electric current. This process offers excellent dyeing performance, cyclic capabilities, and reduces the need of additional chemical reductants [1].

- Foam dyeing technology: Instead of using water, foam dyeing technology uses foam for fabric dyeing. Fabric is padded with foam which contains aqueous dyestuff, foaming agent, and dyestuff carrier. This process allows better dye penetration and fixation, less water and energy consumption, and less waste production than conventional dyeing [46].
- DyStar launched Eco-Advanced Indigo Dyeing technique which aims to reduce water usage by up to 90% and energy consumption by up to 30% during the production process [47].

3.5 Awareness and education

3.5.1 Education for industries:

It is important to educate dye manufacturers and dye-utilizing industries regarding use of eco-friendly dyes, low-impact synthetic dyes, sustainable dyeing techniques, and strategies and practices for waste management by conducting workshops and training programs thereby fostering the adoption of sustainable methods.

3.5.2 Consumer awareness:

Raising awareness among consumers regarding the impacts of synthetic dyes, the importance of adopting and supporting sustainable options, and sustainable clothing brands available, can empower consumers to make informed decisions and direct demand towards sustainable options.

3.5.3 Workers education and safety:

It is crucial to educate and inform workers on the toxic nature and chemical hazards of dyes, safety standards and regulations, and recognize symptoms of exposure to promote a safe working environment. Also, training the workers regarding the use and maintenance of protective equipment, the use of the right tools while dealing with dyes, the use of a ventilation system, handling of any spillage, and safe mixing, transporting, and disposal of dyes, reduces the occupational health risks [48]. Dye industries should provide health services to their workers, including regular health check-ups, access to occupational health services, and immediate treatment for any skin contact.

3.6 Collaborative approaches

Instead of confining to one nation, countries and organizations can pool their knowledge, resources, expertise, technologies, and innovations to deal with the challenges posed by synthetic dyes. Global initiative “Fashion for Good” is a platform that connects sustainable brands, retailers, manufacturers, and funders. It has also launched a digital sustainable dyestuff library and lab for

pilot trials of some innovative dyestuff to ensure their safety for commercial use [49]. Another initiative “Detox My Fashion” campaign by Greenpeace aim to eliminate all toxic chemicals in textile production resulted in around 80 brands and retailers committed to achieve this detox goal [50].

The collaborative approach also involves different industries, government, researchers, and non-governmental organizations working together to achieve the common goal of sustainable dyeing practices. Production of natural dyestuff by sourcing by-products of other industries such as food and agricultural industry offers a sustainable alternative to synthetic dyes along with lower environmental burden, e.g. Archroma introduced EarthColors, a range of seven high performance natural dyes from non-edible agricultural or herbal industries waste such as almond shells, cotton plant residues, bitter orange residues, beet residues and saw palmetto residues, covering a palette of natural warm shades [51]. Sages, a British dye company creates natural dyes from food waste like blueberries, avocado pits, onion skins and red cabbages [52]. Several brands and organizations in India repurpose floral waste from temples and weddings into natural dyes, thus promoting sustainability. These include, MATR (by Praveen Chauhan), Bageeya (by Jigisha Shukla), Temple Blessing Project (by Rupa Trivedi), Nimboo (by Saurabh Mahajan), and Project Palash (by students of Aryabhata College, Delhi University). Another innovative approach is given by Italian textile chemical company Officina+39 by creating powder dyes from the textile waste (both pre and post-consumer) under the name Recycrom [53].

4 Conclusion

Synthetic dyes, while playing major role in various industries, cause significant concern for environment and human health across various stages of their life cycle. Although constant efforts are being made towards sustainable alternatives, but achieving sustainability presents various challenges, including weak regulatory framework, economic constraints, unawareness, limited knowledge and technological limitations. To address these challenges, several steps should be taken, such as strengthen regulatory enforcements related to dyes and dyeing, strict and globally followed prohibition of toxic synthetic dyes use, complete the toxicity knowledge of unexamined synthetic dyes, further R&D for efficient and cost-effective dye effluent treatment method, establish common dye-effluent treatment plants in all industrial areas, closed-loop water system in industries, regular inspection of industries, further R&D to improve extraction and performance of natural dyes, explore more sustainable material sources, raise awareness and education about sustainable dyes and dyeing technologies to foster demand and adoption, active governmental support and initiatives, and encourage slow fashion principle, and adopting other measures. These efforts could help overcome the issue and move towards more sustainable practices that benefit both the environment and the industry.

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